

Humour Styles, Self-esteem, and Subjective Happiness among Young Adults

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Psychological well-being among young adults has gained increasing attention within the framework of positive psychology. The present study examined the relationships among humour styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness, and explored gender differences in humour styles. Using a quantitative correlational design, data were collected from a sample of 76 young adults (38 males & 38 females) aged 18-25 years. Participants completed the Humour Styles Questionnaire (Martin et al., 2003), Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1965), and Subjective Happiness Scale (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999). The results indicated significant positive relationships between adaptive humour styles and self-esteem, with self-enhancing humour ($r = .396, p < .01$) and affiliative humour ($r = .285, p < .05$) showing positive associations. Adaptive humour styles were also positively related to subjective happiness, with significant correlations observed for self-enhancing humour ($r = .352, p < .01$) and affiliative humour ($r = .372, p < .01$). A strong positive relationship was found between self-esteem and subjective happiness ($r = .586, p < .01$). Gender differences were significant for aggressive humour ($t = 2.253, p < .05$) and self-defeating humour ($t = 2.951, p < .05$), while no significant gender differences were found for adaptive humour styles. The findings highlight the importance of adaptive humour and positive self-evaluation as key psychological resources contributing to subjective happiness among young adults.

Keywords: Humour styles, self-esteem, subjective happiness, positive psychology, young adults

Psychological well-being has emerged as a central concern in contemporary mental health research, particularly within the framework of positive psychology, which emphasizes strengths, adaptive functioning, and subjective experiences of happiness (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Among young adults, well-being is influenced by a range of personality and psychosocial factors that shape emotional regulation, interpersonal relationships, and self-evaluation.

Within the framework of positive psychology, psychological well-being is conceptualized as the presence of positive emotions, adaptive functioning, and subjective experiences of happiness (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Humour has been theoretically and empirically examined as a multidimensional construct, with adaptive and maladaptive styles showing differential associations with mental health outcomes (Martin et al., 2003).

Humour is a multifaceted construct that functions as a cognitive, emotional, and social process used to cope with stress and regulate emotions (Martin, 2007). Contemporary research conceptualizes humour in terms of adaptive and maladaptive styles. Adaptive humour styles, such as affiliative and self-enhancing humour, are associated with positive interpersonal relationships and psychological well-being, whereas maladaptive humour styles, including aggressive and self-defeating humour, are linked to poorer mental health outcomes (Martin et al., 2003; Kuiper, Grimshaw,

Leite, & Kirsh, 2004).

Self-esteem reflects an individual's overall evaluation of self-worth and is a key determinant of psychological well-being (Rosenberg, 1965). Subjective happiness refers to individuals' global evaluation of their happiness and life satisfaction (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999). Despite evidence supporting the independent roles of humour styles and self-esteem in well-being, limited research has examined their combined influence on subjective happiness, particularly among Indian young adults. The present study addresses this gap.

Review of Literature

Research consistently shows that adaptive humour styles are positively associated with psychological well-being and life satisfaction, whereas maladaptive humour styles are associated with emotional distress. Foundational work demonstrated that affiliative and self-enhancing humour were linked to positive psychological outcomes, while aggressive and self-defeating humour were associated with poorer adjustment (Martin et al., 2003; Kuiper, Grimshaw, Leite, & Kirsh, 2004). More recent studies have supported these findings, indicating that adaptive humour styles promote emotional resilience and effective coping with stress among young adults (Cann & Collette, 2014; Mesmer-Magnus, Glew, & Viswesvaran, 2012). Contemporary research also suggests that humour plays a significant role in enhancing social connectedness and psychological adjustment across cultures (Wellenzohn, Proyer, & Ruch, 2018).

Self-esteem has been identified as a strong predictor of happiness and well-being. Earlier studies established a strong association between self-esteem and life satisfaction (Diener & Diener, 2009). More recent longitudinal research indicates that self-esteem contributes to emotional stability, resilience, and positive mental health outcomes over time (Orth & Robins, 2014; Sowislo & Orth,

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2013). Studies among young adults further show that individuals with higher self-esteem are better able to cope with stress and maintain subjective happiness (Mann, Hosman, Schaalma, & de Vries, 2004; Trzesniewski, Donnellan, & Robins, 2013).

Gender differences in humour usage have also been reported, with males more likely to engage in aggressive humour while females tend to prefer affiliative humour styles (Lampert & Ervin-Tripp, 2006). More recent research has found similar trends, suggesting that gender differences in humour expression may be shaped by social norms and emotional regulation patterns (Mahood & Simonds, 2016; Proyer, Ruch, & Müller, 2010). Cross-cultural studies further indicate that while humour styles are generally consistent across genders, cultural expectations influence how humour is expressed and interpreted (Wellenzohn et al., 2018).

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the relationship between humour styles and self-esteem among young adults.
- To examine the relationship between humour styles and subjective happiness among young adults.
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- To assess gender differences in humour styles among young adults.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 76 young adults (38 males & 38 females) aged between 18 and 25 years. Participants were recruited using a convenience sampling method from educational institutions. All participants belonged to the young adult age group and voluntarily agreed to take part in the study.

Measures

Humour Styles Questionnaire (HSQ): The Humour Styles Questionnaire developed by Martin et al. (2003) was used to assess four humour styles: affiliative, self-enhancing, aggressive, and self-defeating humour. The scale consists of 32 items rated on a Likert scale and has demonstrated good reliability and validity in previous research.

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES): Self-esteem was measured using the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale developed by Rosenberg (1965). This 10-item scale assesses global self-worth and is widely used in psychological research.

Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS): The Subjective Happiness Scale developed by Lyubomirsky and Lepper (1999) was used to measure individuals' global subjective happiness. The scale consists of four

items that evaluate overall happiness perceptions.

Procedure

Participants were approached and informed about the purpose of the study. Informed consent was obtained before data collection. The questionnaires were administered either in person or through an online platform. Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Ethical standards were followed throughout the study.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Pearson's product-moment correlation to examine relationships among humour styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness. Independent samples t-tests were conducted to assess gender differences in humour styles.

Results

Pearson's product-moment correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships among humour styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness. The results indicated that self-enhancing humour was positively correlated with self-esteem ($r = .396, p < .01$) and subjective happiness ($r = .352, p < .01$). Affiliative humour was also positively correlated with self-esteem ($r = .285, p < .05$) and subjective happiness ($r = .372, p < .01$). Additionally, a strong positive correlation was observed between self-esteem and subjective happiness ($r = .586, p < .01$). These findings suggest that adaptive humour styles and positive self-evaluation are associated with greater subjective happiness among young adults. The correlations among the study variables are presented in Table 1.

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to examine gender differences in humour styles. The results revealed significant gender differences in aggressive humour ($t = 2.253, p < .05$) and self-defeating humour ($t = 2.951, p < .05$). No significant gender differences were found for adaptive humour styles, including affiliative and self-enhancing humour. Gender differences in humour styles are presented in Table 2.

Table 1

Correlations between Humour Styles, Self-Esteem, and Subjective Happiness (N = 76)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Affiliative humour	-	.309**			.285*	.372**
2. Self-enhancing humour	.309**	-			.396**	.352**
3. Aggressive humour			-	.261*		
4. Self-defeating humour			.261*	-		
5. Self-esteem	.285*	.396**			-	.586**
6. Subjective happiness	.372**	.352**			.586**	-

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

Table 2

Gender Differences in Humour Styles among Young Adults (N = 76)

Humour Style	Male (n = 38) M (SD)	Female (n = 38) M (SD)	t	p
Affiliative	40.95 (6.19)	42.08 (9.28)	ns	> .05
Self-enhancing	37.08 (8.22)	36.58 (7.40)	ns	> .05
Aggressive	26.47 (7.27)	27.71 (7.29)	2.253	< .05
Self-defeating	29.08 (7.89)	22.63 (10.92)	2.951	< .05

Note. $p < .05$. $p < .01$. ns = non-significant

Discussion

The present study examined the relationships among humour styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness among young adults, as well as gender differences in humour styles. The findings highlight the significant role of adaptive humour styles and self-esteem in promoting subjective happiness, supporting the central assumptions of positive psychology that adaptive psychological resources enhance well-being.

The results indicated that self-enhancing humour was positively associated with both self-esteem and subjective happiness. This finding suggests that individuals who use humour to maintain a positive outlook in the face of stress are more likely to experience higher self-worth and greater happiness. Self-enhancing humour enables individuals to reinterpret stressful situations in a less threatening manner, thereby fostering emotional resilience and psychological adjustment (Martin et al., 2003; Cann & Collette, 2014). Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, which show that self-enhancing humour acts as a protective factor against stress and negative affect, contributing to overall well-being (Kuiper et al., 2004).

Affiliative humour was also found to be positively related to self-esteem and subjective happiness. This association may be explained by the social function of affiliative humour, which facilitates interpersonal bonding, social acceptance, and supportive relationships. Positive social interactions are known to enhance self-worth and happiness, particularly during young adulthood when peer relationships play a crucial role in emotional development (Martin, 2007). Previous research has consistently shown that affiliative humour is associated with higher levels of life satisfaction and psychological well-being (Cann et al., 2010; Wellenzohn, Proyer, & Ruch, 2018).

A strong positive correlation was observed between self-esteem and subjective happiness, indicating that individuals with a positive self-evaluation tend to perceive their lives as more satisfying and fulfilling. This finding is consistent with earlier research demonstrating that self-esteem is a robust predictor of subjective well-being and emotional stability (Diener & Diener, 2009; Orth & Robins, 2014). Individuals with higher self-esteem are more likely to engage in adaptive coping strategies and maintain a positive emotional balance, which enhances their overall sense of happiness.

The study also revealed significant gender differences in maladaptive humour styles, with differences observed in aggressive and self-defeating humour. These findings may reflect gender-based socialization patterns and cultural norms that influence emotional expression and coping styles. Males may be more likely to engage in aggressive humour as a socially sanctioned form of assertiveness, whereas self-defeating humour may be used as a coping strategy to manage social expectations (Lampert & Ervin-Tripp, 2006). Previous studies have similarly reported gender differences in the use of maladaptive humour styles, suggesting that societal expectations and emotional regulation processes play an important role in shaping humour expression (Mahood & Simonds, 2016).

Overall, the findings align with existing literature emphasizing the importance of adaptive psychological resources in promoting well-being during young adulthood. The results underscore the role of adaptive humour styles and self-esteem as key contributors to subjective happiness, while highlighting the potential negative impact of maladaptive humour styles on psychological functioning.

These findings contribute to the growing body of research within positive psychology by demonstrating how humour and self-evaluation interact to influence happiness among young adults.

Conclusion

The present study underscores the importance of adaptive humour styles and positive self-evaluation in enhancing subjective happiness among young adults. The findings indicate that self-enhancing and affiliative humour styles are positively associated with self-esteem and subjective happiness, highlighting their role as adaptive psychological resources. In contrast, maladaptive humour styles were associated with poorer psychological outcomes, emphasizing the need to understand humour not merely as a coping strategy but as a multidimensional construct with both beneficial and detrimental effects.

From a theoretical perspective, the study contributes to the positive psychology literature by demonstrating how humour styles and self-esteem interact to influence subjective well-being during young adulthood. The findings also have practical implications for mental health promotion and well-being interventions, suggesting that programs aimed at enhancing adaptive humour and self-esteem may foster emotional resilience and happiness among young adults. Such interventions may be particularly beneficial in educational and counselling settings.

Despite its contributions, the study has certain limitations. The use of a relatively small and homogeneous sample limits the generalizability of the findings. Future research could employ larger and more diverse samples, as well as longitudinal designs, to further examine the causal relationships among humour styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness. Exploring cultural influences on humour expression may also provide valuable insights.

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Received January 16, 2026

Revision received February 10, 2026

Accepted February 12, 2026